

Thorium(IV) Complexes with Bidentate Schiff Base Ligands

HRUDANANDA MOHANTA and KAILASH C. DASH*

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Vani Vihar, Bhubaneswar-751 004.

Thorium(V) forms a number of complexes with the bidentate Schiff base ligands (donor set NO) derived by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and *p*-phenetidine. It is observed that the neutral Schiff bases and not their anions are coordinated to central Thorium(IV) atom. The complexes have the general formulae ThL_2X_4 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_3$) or ThL_2X_4 ($\text{X}=\text{NCS}$), where L represents the bidentate Schiff base. All except the iodo complexes are very stable at room temperature. The iodo complexes decompose slowly giving off iodine vapours. The chloro and iodo complexes are 8-coordinated, the thiocyanato complexes contain N-bonded isothiocyanates and are 10-coordinated, whereas the nitrate complexes involve the nitrate groups in bidentate coordination through two oxygen atoms, thus providing examples of 12-coordinated species. All the complexes are diamagnetic. The TGA and DTA data of some of the complexes are presented, and the stoichiometry of decomposition processes determined. In all cases, ThLX_4 , ThX_4 , ThOX_2 and ThO_2 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{NCS}$) are formed as intermediate compounds.

THE coordination chemistry of Thorium(IV) ion has been less extensively investigated¹, even though it presents an excellent area of research because of its possibility of formation of compounds with coordination numbers greater than six, a feature sparingly observed in transition metal chemistry and which has attracted wide attention in recent years²⁻⁴. For a metal ion to achieve a higher coordination number two conditions are to be satisfied^{5,6}—(a) effective size of the metal ion and b) a high positive formal charge (resulting from high oxidation state) of the central metal atom. A high positive formal charge of the central metal atom is necessary in order to prevent an excess amount of negative charge from accumulating on the metal atom as a result of the association with the electrons contributed by a large number of bonding atoms (8 or more.). It has also been shown that for anions like oxygen or fluorine (with an ionic radii of 1.3-1.5 Å^o), a coordination number of 8 or more would be expected provided the ionic radius of the central atom has a size greater than ~0.9 Å^o. The large thorium(IV) ion with the ionic radii of 0.99 Å^o and its high charge of +4, is expected to satisfy the optimum requirements for the formation of compounds with a higher coordination number⁷. As for the ligands, the chelates as a class dominate the area of higher coordination polyhedra in scope, numbers and in kinetic and thermodynamic stability. In fact, the more compact the ligand and the smaller the 'bite' the more effective is the ligand in generating high coordination structures.

Thorium(IV) is an example of class 'a' electron-acceptor, coordinating strongly to the smaller and more electronegative coordinating atoms N, O and F.^{8,9} Thorium(IV) is also known to display a variable stoichiometry from ligand to ligand¹⁰. Keeping in view this large variation in stoichiometry and the possibility of achieving a higher coordination number, it was considered worthwhile to study systematically the formation of complexes of thorium(IV) with various multidentate Schiff base ligands. This paper reports the

results of investigation of a series of thorium(IV) complexes with bidentate Schiff bases (donor set NO) derived by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and *p*-phenetidine. Results of investigations of various multidentate Schiff base ligands with dioxouranium(VI) from this laboratory have already been reported^{11,12}.

Experimental

Materials: Hydrated thorium(IV) chloride and nitrate were BDH reagent grade.

Thorium(IV) iodide and thiocyanate were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ and NaI or KNCS in stoichiometric quantities and filtering off the insoluble nitrate salt. These solutions of ThI_4 and $\text{Th}(\text{NCS})_4$ were used as such.

The ligands were prepared by methods already reported¹¹.

Syntheses of complexes: The complexes were prepared by mixing warm solutions of thorium(IV) salts and the ligand (1 : 2.5). In most cases almost immediately a compound appeared on stirring, and in some cases refluxing for ca 30 min. was necessary. In all cases, the complex formed was suction filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol, then with ether and finally dried *in vacuo*.

Analyses: The C, H, N analyses were carried out by Frau E. Ullrich, Würzburg University, West Germany. The chloride was estimated as AgCl by standard gravimetric methods¹³. The thorium content was determined by igniting a known weight of the complex to ThO_2 .

Physical measurements: The electrical conductivity, i. r. spectra and electronic spectra were recorded as described previously¹¹. The thermogravimetric

measurements were made with a MOM derivatograph (Budapest) which records TG, DTG, DTA and temp (T) simultaneously by photographic methods. The rate of heating was $10^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

The complexes investigated in this work are presented in Table 1, along with their colour, m. p. and analytical data. All the complexes have a fairly high m. p. and are not soluble enough in organic solvents for molecular weight determinations. All, except the iodo complexes, are very stable at room temperature and can be stored without any change for a long time. The iodo complexes appear to decompose giving off iodine vapours when stored for about a week. The molar conductivity measurements were made in MeOH, Me_2CO and MeNO_2 solutions ($\sim 10^{-4}$ – $10^{-5} M$). High values of molar conductivity were observed in MeOH solutions in all cases, indicating a greater solvolysis

A comparison of the values obtained in MeOH with that obtained in Me_2CO and MeNO_2 indicates that all compounds are non-electrolytes, a fact which is substantiated by i. r. spectra. Measurements of conductivity in all cases were made in presence of excess of added triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO) ligand and the results were found unchanged, indicating clearly the covalent bonding of all anions.

An examination of the i. r. spectra of the free ligand and the complexes indicated similarity although in some cases the ligand bands were either split or shifted due to lattice effects or due to departures from idealised symmetry.^{14,15} A strong band assigned to C=N stretch in 1610 – 1600 cm^{-1} region, suggesting the coordination through the azomethine nitrogen and an increase in the bond order of the carbon and nitrogen link. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ is observed at *ca* 1600 cm^{-1} and the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$

TABLE 1—COLOUR, M. P., AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF Th(IV) COMPLEXES

Compound	Empirical formula	Colour	M. P. (°C)	Analysis %			
				Th	C	H	N
Th(H-Sal Tol) ₂ Cl ₂ ^{a)}	ThC ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	Light yellow	> 250	28.1 (29.1)	41.7 (42.2)	3.4 (3.2)	3.9 (3.5)
Th(H-Sal Anis) ₂ Cl ₂ ^{b)}	ThC ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	— do —	> 250	27.4 (28.0)	41.2 (40.5)	3.8 (3.1)	2.9 (3.3)
Th(H-Sal Phen) ₂ Cl ₂ ^{c)}	ThC ₃₀ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	Deep yellow	> 250	27.0 (27.1)	41.6 (42.0)	3.6 (3.5)	3.1 (3.2)
Th(H-Sal Tol) ₂ I ₂	ThC ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	Light yellow	210(D)	20.1 (19.9)	28.3 (28.9)	2.4 (2.2)	2.1 (2.4)
Th(H-Sal Anis) ₂ I ₂	ThC ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	— do —	205(D)	18.9 (19.4)	28.2 (28.1)	2.0 (2.1)	2.4 (2.3)
Th(H-Sal Phen) ₂ I ₂	ThC ₃₀ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	— do —	208(D)	18.0 (19.0)	28.7 (29.4)	2.1 (2.4)	2.2 (2.2)
Th(H-Sal Tol) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	ThC ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₁₄ N ₆	— do —	> 250	24.8 (25.7)	37.4 (37.2)	3.0 (2.9)	9.1 (9.3)
Th(H-Sal Anis) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	ThC ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₁₄ N ₆	— do —	235(D)	24.6 (24.8)	36.0 (35.9)	2.6 (2.8)	8.8 (8.9)
Th(H-Sal Phen) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	ThC ₃₀ H ₃₀ O ₁₄ N ₆	— do —	> 250	23.7 (24.1)	38.0 (37.4)	3.1 (3.1)	8.9 (8.7)
Th(H-Sal Tol) ₂ (NCS) ₄	ThC ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₇ S ₄	Deep yellow	> 250	21.9 (21.7)	50.8 (50.3)	3.9 (3.5)	8.4 (8.5)
Th(H-Sal Anis) ₂ (NCS) ₄	ThC ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₇ S ₄	— do —	240(D)	20.3 (20.2)	48.6 (48.2)	3.6 (3.4)	8.6 (8.5)
Th(H-Sal Phen) ₂ (NCS) ₄	ThC ₃₀ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₇ S ₄	— do —	226(D)	18.7 (19.5)	49.9 (49.5)	4.1 (3.8)	8.4 (8.2)

*Theoretical values in brackets.

(a) % Cl—18.1 (17.8), (b) % Cl—16.9 (17.1), (c) % Cl—16.2 (16.5)

The abbreviations: H-Sal Tol, H-Sal Anis- and H-Sal Phen refer respectively to the Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and *p*-Toluidine, *p*-Anisidine and *p*-phenetidine.

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRA (cm^{-1}) OF POLYATOMIC ANIONS

Complex	Anion Vibrational mode		
	—NCS ⁻ ion		
	ν_1 (C≡N) str.	ν_2 (C—S) str.	
Th (H-Sal Tol) ₂ (NCS) ₄	2040 s	796 s	
Th (H-Sal Anis) ₂ (NCS) ₄	2060 s	800 s	
Th (H-Sal Phen) ₂ (NCS) ₄	{ 2070 m 2030 s	810 s	
	—NO ₃ ⁻ ion (C _{2v})		
	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3
Th (H-Sal Tol) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	1530 sh	1030 s	{ 810 sh 818 s
Th (H-Sal Anis) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	1530 sh	1032 s	807 m
Th (H-Sal Phen) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	1540 sh	1042 s	808 s

The abbreviations: s = sharp, sh = shoulder, m = medium

at about 1280 – 1260 cm^{-1} region. The (Th-N) stretching frequencies are invariably found at *ca* 580 cm^{-1} in all cases. The $\nu(\text{Th-Cl})$ and $\nu(\text{Th-I})$ could not be studied in the present work. Interesting information is obtained from the i. r. spectra regarding the coordination of NO_3^- and SCN^- ions in the complexes.

Eventhough, the NO_3^- ion occupies a low position in the spectrochemical series near the fluoride ion¹⁶, it is known to coordinate in a variety of ways whereby the D_{3h} symmetry of ionic nitrate is lowered to C_{2v} for both monodentate and bidentate (or bridging) coordination^{17,18}, resulting in difficulty in identification of the mode of coordination by i. r. criterion alone. The method based on the magnitude of splitting of ν_3 in D_{3h} into ν_1 and ν_2 of C_{2v} for distinguishing the monodentate or bidentate character has been

challenged.^{19,20} The spectral bands of $[\text{Th L}_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$ (L = bidentate Schiff base) complexes were compared with the known bands of $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{21}$ (observed at 1510, 1293, 1030 and 808 cm^{-1}), in which the bidentate character of the nitrate groups has been established by X-ray²² and neutron-diffraction studies²³. The nitrate complexes exhibited bands at 1530, 1300, 1030 and 808 cm^{-1} region suggesting bidentate character of the NO_3^- groups and a coordination number of 12 around the Th(IV) atom. A 12-coordinate compound of Th(IV), $[\text{Mg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6][\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_6] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was reported earlier²⁴ where the 12 nearest neighbour Oxygen atoms are placed at the corners of a distorted icosahedron.

The pseudohalide ion, SCN^- , is known to form complexes through the 'hard' N-end or the 'soft' S-end or behave as a bridging ligand depending²⁵ on (a) the nature of the central metal, (b) the nature of other ligands in the coordination sphere, (c) environmental control and kinetic (mechanistic) controls. Each of the normal vibrations of the coordinated SCN^- ion e.g. $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{C-S})$ and $\delta(\text{N-C-S})$, provide useful information regarding its mode of bonding²⁶. In our thiocyanate complexes, $[\text{ThL}_3(\text{NCS})_4]$, $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ was observed in the $2070\text{-}2030\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ in the 800 cm^{-1} region, strongly suggesting N-bonded isothiocyanate coordination²⁷, as expected for a 'hard' acid like the Th(IV) ion. No i.r. bands for ionic thiocyanate in these complexes were obtained, thus providing examples of 10-coordinated Th(IV) complexes. Attention may be focussed to the fact that in case of the Cl^- and I^- only 8-coordinated Th(IV) complexes of the type $[\text{ThL}_2\text{X}_4]$ (L = Schiff base and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$ or I^-) were obtained. Such an anomaly may be explained on the basis of size grounds since the thiocyanate group is N-bonded to the metal atom.

The electronic spectra in solution indicated no bands in the 330-750 nm region. The bands obtained below 330 nm correspond to the ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ region and are of little help in elucidating the structure. They are therefore not discussed.

The thermal decomposition of the chloro and isothiocyanate complexes were investigated to get more information about the stoichiometry of the complexes. The stoichiometry of thermal decomposition obtained for the chloro complexes are :

and for the iso-thiocyanato complexes are :

It is significant to observe here that in all cases ThO_2 is obtained as the end product preceded by the oxohalide or oxo (pseudohalide) species, ThOX_2 ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{NCS}$).

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